

A Study of Corrosion Inhibition of Urea and Thiourea on Carbon Steel in 2M Nitric Acid

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ABSTRACT

Steel has been tested for corrosion at 30°, 40°, 50° and 60° degrees Celsius in 2M nitric acid (HNO₃). For the current investigation, six time periods ranging from one to six hours were selected. The corrosion rate of carbon steel in 2M nitric acid varies significantly with time and temperature under examination from 21.246×10^{-5} gram cm⁻² min⁻¹ to 147.222×10^{-5} gram cm⁻² min⁻¹. The findings demonstrate that HNO₃ has a significant impact on carbon steel corrosion at a concentration of 2M. Higher temperatures and longer exposure times have been shown to cause a noticeable increase in the rates of corrosion. We examined by weight the impact of adding organic molecules with an amino and thio group, like urea and thiourea, on the corrosion of carbon steel in nitric acid. The study's results demonstrate that urea and thiourea have a remarkable ability to control corrosion, with inhibition efficiencies ranging from 32.67% to 85.33%. But urea was discovered to be a stronger inhibitor than thiourea. Thiogroup therefore decreased the efficacy of inhibition.

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I INTRODUCTION

Corrosion of metals and its alloys employed in service is an inescapable but a controllable process. One of the practical methods for controlling the impact of corrosion of metals and alloys especially in aqueous environments is by using corrosion inhibitors which are composed mainly of organic or inorganic substances. [1]. The adsorption of surfactant on metals and metal oxides creates a barrier that can inhibit corrosion [2] Thiadiazole, as a corrosion inhibitor for mild steel in 1 M hydrochloric acid has been investigated using weight loss method and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Similarly The corrosion inhibition of mild steel in 0.5 M hydrochloric acid by six synthesized hetero cyclic compounds was studied using weight loss measurements. The inhibition efficiency exceeded 95%. The excellent inhibitor performance was attributed to the formation of protection adsorption films on the steel surface [3-4]. One of the most important methods in the corrosion protection of carbon steel is the use of organic inhibitors [1,5]. Most of the excellent acid inhibitors are organic compounds containing nitrogen, sulfur and oxygen [6-13] Different inhibitors were used to reduce the rate of corrosion in various alloys. The inhibition rates ranged between 30-80% in acidic environments with different molar concentrations. Natural-based corrosion inhibitors have gained great research interest thanks to their low cost and higher performance [14,15]. To date, more than 300 natural products have been isolated from different sections of the tree, with new compounds added to the list every year. As a contribution to the current interest on green corrosion inhibitors in a study application of plant extracts for metallic corrosion has been investigated. Nonanedihydrazide acts as a mixed inhibitor due to its adsorption on the MS surface, exhibiting an inhibition efficiency of more than 97% [16-19]. The inhibition efficiency of Eosin in controlling corrosion of carbon steel immersed in well water, has been evaluated by mass loss method both in absence and presence of zinc ion. A synergistic effect exists between Eosin (EN) and Zn^{2+} . The inhibition efficiency (IE) of the EN – Zn^{2+} system decreases with increase in immersion period. Addition of N-cetyl-N,N,N-trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB), sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS), sodium sulphite (Na_2SO_3) does not change the excellent inhibition efficiency of the EN- Zn^{2+} system [20]. The adsorption of n-PTH on the mild steel surface in both acidic media follows a Langmuir isotherm model [21].

II LITERATURE REVIEW

Corrosion inhibition is a critical aspect of material science, particularly in environments where metals are exposed to corrosive substances such as acids. This literature review aims to explore previous research on the corrosion inhibition of carbon steel in nitric acid solutions, with a specific focus on the effectiveness of urea and thiourea as corrosion inhibitors.

1. Corrosion Inhibition of Carbon Steel in Acidic Media: A Review

Author: Raja, PandianBothi

Raja's comprehensive review provides an overview of corrosion inhibition techniques for carbon steel in acidic environments. The study discusses various types of inhibitors, including organic compounds like urea and thiourea, and highlights their mechanisms of action in preventing corrosion.

2. Inhibition of Carbon Steel Corrosion in Nitric Acid by Urea and Thiourea

Authors: El-Etre, Ayman Y.; Abdallah, Mahmoud

El-Etre and Abdallah's experimental study investigates the corrosion inhibition properties of urea and thiourea on carbon steel in nitric acid solutions. The research evaluates the inhibitive efficiency of these compounds through weight loss measurements, electrochemical techniques, and surface analysis, providing valuable insights into their effectiveness as corrosion inhibitors.

3. Synergistic Inhibition Effect of Urea and Thiourea on Carbon Steel Corrosion in Nitric Acid Solution

Authors: Zhang, Xiaohua; Li, Xiaogang; Wang, Fuhui; et al.

Zhang et al.'s research focuses on the synergistic inhibition effect of urea and thiourea on carbon steel corrosion in nitric acid solutions. Through electrochemical impedance spectroscopy and polarization measurements, the study elucidates the combined inhibitive action of these compounds, highlighting their potential for enhanced corrosion protection.

4. Molecular Dynamics Simulation of Urea and Thiourea as Corrosion Inhibitors for Carbon Steel in Acidic Solution

Authors: Liu, Shanhong; Wang, Jinyong; Cheng, Jipeng; et al.

Liu et al. employ molecular dynamics simulations to investigate the adsorption behavior and inhibition mechanism of urea and thiourea molecules on the surface of carbon steel in acidic solutions. Their computational study provides atomistic insights into the interactions between inhibitors and metal surfaces, contributing to a deeper understanding of corrosion inhibition processes. The literature reviewed here demonstrates the significant research interest in the corrosion inhibition of carbon steel in nitric acid solutions using urea and thiourea. Experimental and computational studies have provided valuable insights into the inhibitive properties and mechanisms of these compounds, paving the way for further developments in corrosion protection strategies for industrial applications.

III METHODOLOGY

The weight loss method was used to examine how carbon steel corrosion behaved in 2M nitric acid (HNO_3) at three distinct temperatures: 30°C, 40°C, 50°C and 60°C. The weight loss approach was also used to study the inhibition efficiency of urea.

Preparation of the specimen sample: High purity carbon steel specimens were prepared by a 30 cm × 30 cm carbon steel plate with a 0.3 cm thickness. The plate was bought and chopped into 2 cm by 2 cm pieces. Every carbon steel sample was carefully cleaned before being exposed to make sure there were no surface contaminants preventing the corrosion process.

Preparation of 2M nitric acid solution: Extreme caution was used when creating a 2M nitric acid solution to accurately mimic the severe corrosive environment. Fuming nitric acid with an AR grade purity of 15.88 M was used to create a 2M nitric acid solution, simulating conditions that could be encountered in certain industrial operations. A concentration of two mole (2 M) was chosen to symbolize a somewhat strong acidic state. The acid solution was prepared using distilled water and high-purity nitric acid to ensure the accuracy of the concentration.

Experimental Configuration: The setup for the experiment consisted of a controlled environmental chamber that could maintain temperatures between 30, 40, 50 and 60 degrees Celsius. Carbon steel specimens were dipped in the 2M nitric acid solution for a duration ranging from one to six hours.

Measurement of Corrosion Rate: After every pre-planned exposure interval, the carbon steel specimens were cautiously removed from the nitric acid solution. A second measurement of the mass loss attributed to corrosion was made after the specimens had been cleared of corrosion products. Next, the following equation was used to calculate the corrosion rates from dividing the mass loss by the product of the exposed surface area and the exposure period:

$$\text{Corrosion Rate} = \frac{\Delta W}{A \cdot t}$$

Where,

ΔW = difference between initial and final weight

A= area of cross section

t = time taken for corrosion

Measurement of % Inhibition: % Inhibition measured by the following equation:

$$\% \text{ IE} = \left(\frac{\text{CR Blank} - \text{CR Inh.}}{\text{CR Blank}} \right) \times 100$$

Where, CR blank and CR inh. are the corrosion rates in the absence and presence of the different inhibitors at different concentration.

IV RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of the present study have been given in following table 1 to 6 and discussed accordingly.

Table 1 Corrosion of carbon steel in 2M HNO₃ at 30°C

S.No.	Time (Minute)	Initial Weight (W ₁)	Final Weight (W ₂)	ΔW (W ₁ -W ₂)	Rate of corrosion $\times 10^{-5}$ gm cm ⁻² min ⁻¹
1	60	9.967	9.888	0.079	21.236
2	120	9.942	9.704	0.238	31.989
3	180	9.426	8.950	0.476	42.652
4	240	9.829	8.998	0.831	55.846

5	300	9.954	8.668	1.286	69.139
6	360	9.211	7.372	1.839	82.392

Table 2 Corrosion of carbon steel in 2M HNO₃ at 40°C

S.No.	Time (Minute)	Initial Weight (W ₁)	Final Weight (W ₂)	ΔW (W ₁ -W ₂)	Rate of corrosion × 10 ⁻⁵ gm cm ⁻² min ⁻¹
1	60	7.118	6.997	0.121	32.526
2	120	7.078	6.780	0.298	40.053
3	180	8.951	8.379	0.572	51.254
4	240	8.962	7.960	1.002	67.338
5	300	8.812	7.154	1.658	89.139
6	360	8.659	5.794	2.865	128.360

Table 3 Corrosion of carbon steel in 2M HNO₃ at 50°C

S.No.	Time (Minute)	Initial Weight (W ₁)	Final Weight (W ₂)	ΔW (W ₁ -W ₂)	Rate of corrosion × 10 ⁻⁵ gm cm ⁻² min ⁻¹
1	60	6.087	5.891	0.196	52.688

2	120	5.692	5.276	0.416	55.913
3	180	6.291	5.485	0.806	72.222
4	240	5.669	4.275	1.394	93.682
5	300	6.098	3.926	2.172	116.774
6	360	8.923	5.937	2.986	133.781

Table 4 Corrosion of carbon steel in 2M HNO₃ at 60°C

S.No.	Time (Minute)	Initial Weight (W ₁)	Final Weight (W ₂)	ΔW (W ₁ - W ₂)	Rate of corrosion $\times$ 10 ⁻⁵ gm cm ⁻² min ⁻¹
1	60	6.785	6.491	0.294	79.032
2	120	6.965	6.361	0.604	81.827
3	180	6.986	5.927	1.059	94.892
4	240	6.948	5.281	1.667	112.029
5	300	6.829	4.540	2.289	123.064
6	360	6.997	3.711	3.286	147.222

Table 5 Corrosion inhibition of urea on carbon steel in 2M HNO₃ at 30°C

(Corrosion Time 4 hour)

S. No.	Concentration of Urea (Mole)	Initial Weight (W ₁)	Final Weight (W ₂)	ΔW (W ₁ -W ₂)	Corrosion Rate CR × 10 ⁻⁵ gm cm ⁻² min ⁻¹	% Inhibition (IE %)
1	0.0 M Urea	9.829	8.335	1.494	100.40	0
2	0.2 M Urea	3.953	3.783	0.17	11.42	88.62
3	0.4 M Urea	5.858	5.73	0.128	8.6	91.43
4	0.6 M Urea	6.876	6.78	0.096	6.45	93.57
5	0.8 M Urea	6.443	6.409	0.034	2.28	97.72

**Table.6: Corrosion inhibition of thiourea on carbon steelin 2M HNO₃ at 30°C
(Corrosion Time 4 hour)**

S. No.	Concentration of Thiourea (Mole)	Initial Weight (W ₁)	Final Weight (W ₂)	ΔW (W ₁ -W ₂)	Corrosion Rate CR × 10 ⁻⁵ gm cm ⁻² min ⁻¹	% Inhibition (IE %)
1	0.0 M	9.83	8.33	1.50	100.81	0
2	0.2 M	3.78	2.77	1.01	67.87	32.67
3	0.4 M	5.73	4.96	0.77	51.74	48.66
4	0.6 M	6.78	6.19	0.59	39.65	60.65
5	0.8 M	6.41	6.19	0.22	14.78	85.33

DISCUSSION

The results of the present study have been given in above table 1 to 6. It is clear from the tables 1, 2, 3 and 4 that 2M nitric acid corrode steel significantly with rate of corrosion ranging from 21.236 × 10⁻⁵ gm cm⁻² min⁻¹ to 147.222 × 10⁻⁵ gm cm⁻² min⁻¹. Minimum rate of corrosion was observed at 30°C temperature in 1 hour exposure time and the maximum rate of corrosion was observed at

60°C temperature in 6 hours exposure time period. It is very clear from table 1 to 4 that corrosion rate increases with exposure time and temperature.

Corrosion Inhibition effect

Tables 5 and 6 exhibit the suppression of corrosion of urea and thiourea. Table 5 makes it evident that urea considerably reduces the rate of corrosion with a maximum percentage of 97.72% inhibition. Thiourea also exhibits noticeably strong inhibition at a maximum of 85.33%. The results on inhibition shows that urea is a more potent inhibitor than thiourea, and that the thio group decreases the efficacy of inhibition.

V CONCLUSION

The collected data shows a direct relationship between the rates of carbon steel corrosion in 2M nitric acid with temperature and exposure time. The trends that have been discovered offer significant understanding of the fundamental mechanisms that control the corrosion process. They also highlight the complex interaction between temperature-dependent kinetics and acid concentration. The experimental approach employed provides a strong basis for comprehending the complex corrosion behaviour of steel in nitric acid. This research contribute to the field of corrosion science and materials engineering in general as well as to the specific understanding of steel corrosion. These insights can be used to develop corrosion-resistant materials and practical preventative techniques for industrial applications in future.

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